

THE THEORY OF CHOREOGRAPHIC ART AS AN INTEGRAL PART OF THE PRACTICAL ACTIVITY OF YOUNG CHOREOGRAPHERS

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Abstract: This article examines the importance of in-depth study of the theory of specialized disciplines, which ensures the ability to assimilate the flow of modern information and develop skills in research activity, as well as individual and independent work.

Keywords: dance, creativity, choreography, art, knowledge, theory, practice, forms and content, school, heritage, ballet master, performer, professionalism

Choreographic art is an integral part of the spiritual life of modern society and represents a sphere of social activity where the creative experience of the younger generation finds its organic expression within professional art. Every nation has a rich history closely connected with dance. It is a vivid and colorful creation that serves as an emotional, artistic, and unique reflection of the centuries-old and diverse life of a people, embodying creative imagination. The significance of dance is great—it reflects traditions connected with the life, thoughts, and feelings of a people. The dance of each nation is distinguished by its own specific vocabulary, techniques, manner, and style of performance, as well as expressive positions combined with a clear rhythm. Based on knowledge of the nature of dance and the experience of professional choreographers—who represent a school of mastery in dance creation—the younger generation learns the logic of compositional structure, conciseness, and stage expressiveness of various dances. This naturally allows one to maintain style, manner, and character, and enables a talented choreographer to develop their own artistic handwriting and style.

Today, in order to preserve cultural heritage and pass traditions on to a new generation, extensive and meticulous scientific work is being carried out at the State Academy of Choreography of Uzbekistan to train professional personnel—future leaders of choreographic groups. A significant contribution to the study of the rich heritage of choreographic art and its implementation in practice is made by the scientific monographs of Doctors of Art Studies (PhD) Gulyasal Usmanova, “Trends in the Development of Uzbek Dance Art during the Years of Independence”, and Shirin Jalilova, “Artistic Principles and Techniques of Stage Dance.” Educational manuals by professors of the State Academy of Choreography

of Uzbekistan K.S.Sagatov, I.G. Gorlina and associate professors D.M. Abdukhakimova, M. Makhmudova, A.A. Magdieva, D.M. Yunusova emphasize the importance of further developing scientific theory and its interconnection with the creative practice of choreography specialists. The wide application of modern and advanced teaching methods evolves into pathways of scientific and creative research, when students develop motivation for independent creative search and initiative. This stimulates the imagination of future choreographers, helps reveal hidden creative potential, and fosters a research-oriented approach to learning. In-depth study of theoretical disciplines provides the ability to process modern information flows and develop skills in research activity, as well as individual and independent work. The transfer of creative experience by teachers ensures high-quality education that meets contemporary requirements. Students not only attempt to create but also to impress others with new solutions in the field of choreography. Today, students and teachers of the academy have prepared large choreographic compositions and national performances such as “Jaloliddin Manguberdi,” “Chulpan,” “Bygone Days,” “Bahrom and Dilorom,” “Isadora,” as well as children’s fairy tales like “Beauty and the Beast” and “Aladdin’s Magic Lamp.” These choreographic works were clearly and effectively presented to the audience in the form originally envisioned by the student choreographers.

Today, choreography is one of the forms of stage art that has a wide variety of types and forms, developing across different directions and genres. It is important to remember that the synthetic nature of choreography is rich in content and imagery within choreographic text and the integrity of a dance work. The way it is revealed directly depends on the choreographer’s choice of form, genre, and compositional techniques during the creation and artistic staging process. Choreographic art does not stand still but is in constant development. It is a multifaceted, complex concept that requires specific methods and skills. To master even the basic skills of staging work, it is necessary to know scientific theory and continuously attempt to develop one’s own methods and techniques and implement them in practice. A student choreographer must clearly understand dance and musical dramaturgy, scenography, stage lighting, and possess the fundamentals of dance composition, as well as the ability to create a unified system called dance. Careful theoretical study of new methodological developments in dance composition, along with practical training in specialized classes, allows students to better understand the entire creative process, build effective strategies and tactics for implementing choreographic ideas, and ultimately achieve the desired result on stage.

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